

HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT: CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES

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Abstract

Human resources are the most important resource in an organization. A firm's survival, its success largely depends upon the quality of its human resource. Most problems and challenges in an organization's are people related. Environment is ever changing and so the role of human resource manager is becoming more and more challenging. Despite the use of technology in modern business, Human resources are still adaptive resources of the organization. The research paper highlights on the challenges faced by the human resource manager and the strategies to be adopted to face the changing scenario.

Keywords: *Human resources, challenges, strategies, environment.*

Introduction:

There are various factors of production namely Materials, Machinery, money, methods and Men, in which Men occupies an important place. All other factors will not help the organization to achieve its goals unless there is an effective coordination and utilization of human resources. A good personnel management always make efficient the overall management of the organization. The importance of human factor in any type of organization is due to its unique characteristics. This is only resource which is able to produce an output greater than its input through creativity. Human resource appreciates in value with the passage of time whereas other resources generally depreciate.

Each individual is different from other in terms of physical, psychological, distinct background and so on. The dedication, loyalty, attitude towards the work is also different. So to manage such human resources is to understand their actions, attitudes, needs and urges which is a great challenge faced by human resource managers.

Human Resource Management has evolved considerably over the past century, and experienced a major transformation in form of sustained competitive advantage for organizations operating in a global economy In this paper, we would be discussing the various challenges that HR is facing in today's corporate scenario and some strategies which, if adopted, can help the HRM to sustain better in the challenging and dynamic scenario.

Objectives:

1. To study the concept of HRM
2. To study the challenges faced by HR Managers.
3. To provide strategies to overcome challenges.

Emerging HR challenges:

- **Technological Advances:** Technological advances have a significant impact on human resources. The organization need of skilled personals, technologically advance manpower,

equipments in order to survive in a competitive environment. Some of the organisations can also go for automation and expansion of business. So the need of qualified, experienced and skilled manpower is a challenge.

- **Developing The Leaders of Tomorrow:** HR managers can develop employees into leaders of tomorrow. This can save the cost of recruitment and training at the same time the there is strong attachment of the person with the organization since working for a pretty long time. There is a need of mentoring the current employees who can become the leader tomorrow. But sometimes it becomes a great challenge because the Relationship between the managers and employees is not that good.
- **Diverse Workforce:** Today the organization is dealing with people from different age, gender, educational background, and income, marital and work experience. Due to cultural differences and habits there is difficulty in communication and a rise in the friction. Managing these people with different religious, cultural, moral background is challenging task for HR Manager.
- **Training and development:** The human resource department faces many challenges in employees' training and development. There are some high potential employees who after training can bring good performance in the organization but at the same time their stability is a big threat. Some are low performers which does not effect by any training programs. Investing in the training and development of such lower performers is another problem.
- **Work Life Balance:** Work-Life Balance is the degree to which an individual can simultaneously balance the emotional, behavioral and time demands of paid work, family and personal duties. Over the past few decades there has been change in the work pattern because of which the life of many employees today is becoming more complex. There is an increased burden of family and other personal responsibilities. There is a great challenge for the HR managers to understand the difficulties faced by the employees in balancing their organizational task with their family time and health.
- **Conflict Managing:** Every individual have different opinions, thought processes, attitudes, interests, needs in an organization. If they find it difficult to adjust with each other, conflict arises. It is a great challenge to the organization to survive if the employees are constantly engaged in fights and conflicts. A conflict brings tensions and depressions and reduces productivity. HR managers should know how to handle employee-employer and employee-employee conflicts without hurting their feelings.
- **Retaining employee:** Globalization has brought freedom to working professionals to work anywhere in the world. There is free mobility of human resources from one organization to another. Many big organizations attract the talent by offering lucrative opportunities to work. So retaining the best industry talents is no joke.

Strategies:

- **Technological Advances:** The HR manager should pay attention to what other companies are adopting. Talk to the technical team frequently and align the technology according to the needs of the organization. The HR manager should encourage the team and employees to build business

plans and ideas based on the latest tech. The manager should try to communicate frequently and transparently before, during, and after periods of change. He should also equip employees with the skills and competencies they will need to respond to and overcome it.

- **Developing The Leaders of Tomorrow:** HR Manager should provide specific training sessions to talented individuals. Show employees a clear progression path ahead of them; this will motivate them staying in an organization. They should develop their interpersonal skills. Give the employee opportunities to lead and present to the team and be open-minded and inclusive.
- **Diverse Workforce:** Organization should celebrate cultural diversity by conducting various cultural activities, celebrate different festivals and organize games to help employees understand new and diverse backgrounds. Efforts should be on team building activities and focus on common objectives.
- **Training and development:** The employees should be provided with well equipment and tools for their jobs. At the same time upskill and train the employees to be familiar with the latest tools and technologies. Go for delegation and decentralization. Encourage the employees to relax and also, dedicate some time for self-care.
- **Work Life Balance:** Factors like Infrastructure, Leaves, Assistance, Motivation, Self-Time, Targets etc. should be focused. Go for digitalization and upgraded technology to make the work easier and fast. A HR manager should encourage a culture of openness. More flexibility in working condition can help the employees to balance their work life. They should create opportunities for its employees to use their skills and strengths every day. Accomplishing goals will motivate them and give them a chance to develop their skills.
- **Conflict Managing:** HR managers should know how to handle superior-subordinate and peer-team conflicts without hurting their feelings. It is almost impossible to completely avoid conflicts among people but handling them tactfully can help HR managers to resolve the issues. They should be able to listen to each party, decide and communicate to them in a convincing manner in order to avoid future conflicts.
- **Retaining employee:** Select the right candidate for the job leads to job satisfaction and this can help to reduce the attrition rate. Time to time training to the employees will enhance their knowledge and skill and also their performance. Try to provide a friendly atmosphere to the employees which will retain them with the organization. Always conduct exit interviews to understand the reason an employee is leaving the company.

Conclusion:

The HRM in today's era has to scale up the expertise and capabilities that are needed to gain a competitive edge on global scale. It depends highly on HR to face the challenges of globalization which has given an entirely new view to organizations. Not only globalization effects but also other factors like technological changes, competency of existing employees, laws and regulations regarding employee benefits and increasing competition in business environment. HR manager must go for continuous creativity and innovation and must keep in mind the challenges while recruiting and selection of the best employee.

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